

COMPOSITION OF BOILED OIL. A PRELIMINARY NOTE.

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In a previous paper on the subject, one of us (*Science and Culture*, 1935, 1, 183) put forward that the chemical change, when boiled oil is prepared from linseed oil in presence of catalysts like oleates, linoleates or rosinate of manganese, cobalt, lead or nickel, consists in the formation of compounds containing conjugated double bonds; and in the case of linolenic acid residue there is rearrangement of double bonds to form alternate single and double ones:

Experiments have now been done to verify this and other views (*loc. cit.*). It has been found that when linseed oil of nil Diene number is boiled in presence of catalysts under the conditions of technical boiling pan with regulated supply of air, the Diene value* gradually increases indicating the formation of compounds containing conjugated double bonds.

Experiments are now being done with finely divided metals to verify other points, *viz.*,

- (i) In the boiled oil pan it is the finely divided metals which really act as catalysts.
- (ii) Olein and linolein or the oils containing them in presence of salt catalysts or the corresponding finely divided metals and air form first (a) hydroxy compounds then by elimination of H_2O , (b) unsaturated compounds and finally, by rearrangements of double bonds, (c) compounds containing conjugated double bonds.

* $\frac{a-b}{e} \times 1.269$, where a = no. of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH required to neutralise 10 c.c. of 1% solution of maleic anhydride heated in a sealed tube in blank experiment; b = no. of c.c. of $N/10$ -NaOH required to neutralise the excess of 10 c.c. of 1% solution of maleic anhydride which remains when oil is heated with it in a sealed tube; e = weight of oil in g. (*vide Kaufmann and Baltes, Fette u. Seifen, 1936, 48, 93.*)

(iii) Linolein or oils containing it under the same conditions may produce directly (c) of (ii).

The changes of (ii) and (iii) may be represented thus :

(Olein)

or

(Linolein)

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Received January 26, 1937.